

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D2.3 Prototype of Crop-health Kit

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ACRONYMS LIST

CHSK	Crop-Health Sensor Kit
CSU	Communications and Storage Unit
DIY	Do it yourself
MMSK	Multi-modal Sensor Kit
NCK	Nutrient-Content Kit

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the main technical objectives of the GOhydro project is the development of a Multi-modal Sensor Kit (MMSK) capable of monitoring at pre-determined intervals the environmental factors affecting the hydroponic cultures of microgreens, the quality of the water feeding the plants as well as the nutrient content of the microgreens. This kit has as a main task to collect information about the cultivation conditions and the quality of the microgreens and communicate the relevant information to the mobile application of the agronomist that will notify the user about the health of the crops and provide suggestions about necessary condition arrangements. Towards that end the MMSK is divided into 3 major components: **(1) the Crop Health Sensor Kit (CHSK)** responsible for monitoring the temperature, humidity, light intensity at the installation as well as the electroconductivity and PH of the water in the tank (indicating the quality of the watering), **(2) a photonics-based kit that will determine the nutrient content of the microgreens through their pulps (Nutrient-content Kit, NCK),** and **(3) the communications and storage unit (CSU)** that stores and transmits the data collected by the kits to the GOhydro data-driven platform. The MMSK is developed through a dedicated work package (WP2), which has received input from WP1 “Nutrient and environmental needs for microgreens” with regards to the specific parameters that must be monitored for a successful hydroponic installation.

This deliverable is the description of the first component of the MMSK, namely the Crop-Health Sensor Kit with the accompanying CSU and is the outcome of Task 2.3. Even though the actual deliverable D2.3 is a DEMOSNTRATOR, it was deemed necessary by the partners involved in WP2 to also provide this accompanying document that analyzes in detail the overall design concept and the entire design procedure, which were essential to the realization of the two components. As a result, D2.3 is divided into 3 Chapters, the first describing the design concept, the second enlisting the kit components and the third demonstrating in detail the design process from the ideation to the final design selection.

1 DESIGN CONCEPT

GOhydro as a whole aims at developing a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in an urban setting. GOhydro aspires to culminate in the production of a platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all tool, applicable to all forms of urban farming. With this aim in mind, the GOhydro platform has a “dual core” one that consists of the platform's hardware and one that consists of the AI component. The former, collectively described as the MMSK, is the core that in essence monitors, collects and transmits the data pertinent to the health and nutrient content of the hydroponically cultivated microgreens and can be envisaged as the “front-end” of the GOhydro platform responsible for the continuous monitoring of all parameters for the successful cultivation of plants at the hydroponic installation (Fig. 1.1). Apart from the monitoring and collection of data, this front-end will also be responsible for the data transmission to the computational back-end of the platform.

The CHSK is one of the three major components of the MMSK and has as its main task the measurement of the environmental parameters along the water quality and nutrition content.

Figure 1.1. Schematic Representation of the GOhydro platform concept. The CHSK is represented by the dashed boxes and serves as part of the front-end (input) of the GOhydro platform alongside the NCK (shown in green)

The design concept of the CHSK was based on two basic pillars:

1. The identification environmental and nutrient parameters that must be monitored and are essential for the successful hydroponic cultivation of 3 microgreens (basil, broccoli and Brussels sprouts). These parameters were determined by the findings of WP1 “Nutrient and environmental needs for microgreens” and in particular Task1.1 “Review on nutrient and production parameters and light requirements”
2. The basic concept that underlies the entire GOhydro project is the development of an efficient and cost-efficient tool that can allow anyone to create his/her own hydroponic installation and have a personalized monitoring tool. As such, all components must be of low cost, off-the-shelf, and easily accessible (i.e. can be directly ordered through e-commerce), while the entire installation and kits (except the NCK) can be assembled in a DIY fashion. With these two basic prerequisites the monitoring parameters were selected and the components specified in D2.1 “Multi-modal Sensor Kit Specifications and Requirements”, which was concluded within Task 2.1 “Sensor kits specification and requirements” and receiving continuous input from Task 1.1. “Review on nutrient and production parameters and light requirements”. Nonetheless, Task 2.3 “Crop health sensor kit” continued to receive information from Task 1.1 as well as partial findings of Task 1.2 “Evaluation of optimised growth environments in controlled experiments” in order to optimize all design aspects of the CHSK. In addition, during the tri-weekly progress meetings the entire consortium contributed

to the design and selection of individual feature starting from the ideation prepared by nr21 all the way to final fine-tuning of all design aspects.

This iterative and collaborative process resulted in a slightly different design than the one originally conceived when the requirements and specifications were collected (D2.1). The deviation from the original concept was that the two separate sub-units (see D2.1), one measuring the environmental conditions and one the water quality, were merged into a single unit (Figure 1.2). This twist was proven to be more cost-efficient and more ergonomic. More details will be provided in Section 3. It should be emphasized at this point that the materials selected for the encasing of the now “all-in-one” kit are compatible with 3d-printers so as to allow anyone to fabricate and assemble their own kit. In order to better demonstrate the feasibility as a DIY kit, the first CHSK will be fabricated at SciO –and not outsourced- based on the designs of nr21 and tested with the aid of NCSR.D.

ALTERNATIVE IDEA All-in-one monitor

An idea is to combine the Water and Nutrition Quality Unit with Environmental Monitoring Unit to one monitoring Unit. This way we only need one housing, one microcontroller and battery by bundling the data transfer to the Communications and Storage Unit. An All-In-One unit in our perspective will have its biggest advantages in the ease of use.

16 April 2021

HYDROPONIC INSTALLATION WITH ALL-IN-ONE MONITOR 3D Overview

16 April 2021

Figure 1.2. Characteristic shots from the Design Brief organized by nr21 demonstrating the updated concept of the all-in-one monitoring CHSK.

2 COMPONENTS

The components had already been selected since M3 when D2.1 was completed. They are though listed once more in this section to facilitate the presentation of the design process.

Table 1. All-in-one Crop-health Sensor Kit Components

Electroconductivity Sensor. Analog TDS Sensor Water Conductivity Sensor
Water Temperature Sensor. Temperature Sensor – Waterproof (LM35)
Air Temperature & Humidity Sensor Adafruit Si7021 Temperature & Humidity Sensor Breakout Board
Microcontroller Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (BLE, WiFi & Ethernet onboard)
Battery Xiaomi Redmi 18W Fast Charge 20000mAh

Table 2. Communication and Storage Unit Components

Microcontroller. Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (BLE, WiFi & Ethernet onboard)
Charging. Plugged-in to conventional power socket

3 DESIGN PROCESS

The modular Crop Health Sensor Kit is part of a smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow to optimize the harvest. The Crop Health Sensor Kit should allow any user to set up a hydroponic culture at their urban setting of choice. Therefore, it should be low cost, easy to use and easy to install.

In order to have an efficient and outcome-focused design process, we gathered the status quo input as well as expectations, requirements and detailed information about development work that has already been carried out. The profound understanding of the full context of the product parameters help to make the design work tailored to its use case while having a lean, agile and efficient development process at the same time.

Together with the project partners we collected and aligned the usability-related and technical aspects, which influence the structure of the hardware design, such as:

- Requirements and expectations for the targeted GOhydro units
- Detailed information of all components
- Basic layout approaches of the housing and its assembly concept
- UX related parameters
- Use-case environment

The next step was the translation of all collected influencing parameters into a spatial solution. The resulting dimensions have a major impact on handling, installation and ultimately the shape. In addition we set the aim to achieve design consistency for the targeted GOhydro units that create a coherent appearance, which leads to a recognizable and differentiated GOhydro design language.

Figure 3.1. Space claims for Crop Health Sensor Kit

constraint that required spatial separation of certain components. We finally decided to avoid duplicating infrastructure and additional housing manufacturing via 3D printing, and that's how the idea of turning the concept

The initial idea of the project team was to treat the CHSK and NCK as two separated devices accompanied by the CSU. The first step was to make a study for the space claim based on the selected components as identified in D2.1 and listed in Chapter 2. Figures 3.1 and 3.2 show the results of this first design step. The analysis of all the necessary space requirements and the power consumption of the electrical components led to the idea of significantly simplifying the overall concept. It became clear that the power bank is the main driver of the housing volume and the associated external dimensions, but at the same time the power consumption was not estimated to be very high. The interval of the values to be determined, which influence plant growth, can also be set at a longer time interval, which saves additional energy. All other components are rather small and there was no technical

into an all-in-one sensor kit was born. This simplification step required a minor change in the hardware layout, which was confirmed by the project partners.

Figure 3.2. The communications and storage unit (CSU) was only treated as a “placeholder box” at this stage as it was less relevant in terms of layout and installation options.

The advantages of the change of concept are:

- Cost reduction
- Less parts
- Faster manufacturing (3D print)
- Easier installation for the user (less devices have to be mounted)

The CHSK henceforth consists of two units (shown together in Fig. 3.3):

- The Water and Nutrition Quality & Environmental Monitoring Unit (All-in-one).
- Communications and storage unit (central communications hub).

Figure 3.3. Space claims for All-in-one CHSK (left) and CSU (right)

After we clarified all the structural requirements for the determination of the spatial requirements, the development of a formal solution began. We were concerned with the following points:

- The form-finding taking into account the manufacturing approach via 3D printing, good usability
- The formal differentiation from conventional DIY kits
- Consideration of installation near hydroponic crops
- Integration of appropriate seals to protect against moisture
- The integration of the components in the simplest and most user-friendly way possible

Even if we were still working with placeholder geometries at this point, relatively precise assumptions could already be made about the design. Different variants were considered with different advantages in terms of mounting on the planted shelf and the number of housing parts and finally the associated formal advantages.

In more detail, the design ideation followed the following steps:

1. Underlying Concept: The hydroponic installation is a simple set up that include persons without any related pre-knowledge as the target group to grow plants in their homes. The basic setup includes a shelving unit with grid shelves for drainage, trays (including grow pads), an aquarium with pump and airstone and tubes to transport the water to the top tray for watering the plants and hydroponic lamps for lighting. The Environmental Monitoring unit should be located in a way that it can catch a representative value of light distributed inside the installation (Figure 3.4).

ION

Figure 3.4. Finalized underlying design concept of the GOhydro all-in-one CHSK and CSU. The drawing also depicts the chosen location of placement

- 2. Design Considerations:** (i) **Indoor gardening references:** Observing a trend towards a simple and minimalist appearance for smart indoor gardening products that follow the consumer device trends, we wanted to apply a *corresponding design language that aim to provide a simplistic user experience*; (ii)

materials and processing: Regarding materials and processing, we wanted an approach to *minimize or to completely avoid tooling costs*. Therefore, we considered *3D printing* is a very suitable manufacturing process for small quantities without geometrical limitations. In order to produce the device hardware housing, 3D printing allows to leverage different materials from flexible to hard resins. The more resin types we use, the more difficult it will be to have the cases manufactured by users in a DIY approach.

(iii) housing assembly and sealing: A very important consideration was to make a very conscious choice between a “*splash-proof*” or “*damp-proof*” housing. This was an important requirement decision, which has a direct effect over the complexity of the housing design and the used materials. The reason behind the choice lies on the fact that the more advanced the product sealing must be, the more precise the production is and the more materials have to be specialized for this purpose. Therefore, a compromise had to be made to keep the sealing satisfactory without increasing the cost. Several sealing options were considered and discussed (Figure. 3.5)

Figure 3.5. Sealing options examined for the GOhydro CHSK assembly

3. **Interaction of the user with the hardware:** On a high-level perspective, we had 3 main interaction scenarios for the devices. These scenarios were most relevant for the design and the usability of the device. It was important to understand that the more one strives for a DIY design approach, the less complexity can be implemented for the device interaction and the more limited the design is able to support the device interaction requirements. The three main interaction requirements were **(i) Installation and setup.** The installation and the setup of the device must be easy to communicate, intuitive and reliable. **(ii) Interaction during operation:** The interaction with the device during operation must be limited to the minimum. In case there are use cases when the interaction with the hardware becomes relevant the interfaces should be obvious, intuitive and easy to access. **(iii) Charging:** The charging of the battery is the use case that presented the biggest challenges for the design as the battery needs to be sealed and also easily accessible.

Based on all the above, the design focused in particular on the following aspects:

1. Installation- Shelf Unit

The Ikea Omar metal shelves, which were chosen for the DIY hydroponic installation already realized at the premises of SCiO (Figure 3.6a) with its curved lattice elements are very suitable for fixing the unit on the vertical

bars (Figure 3.6b,c). Three unit footprints (Designs 01-03) that seemed most appropriate for the unit housing were examined, with the first one having two variations (Designs 01A and 01B). All designs are shown in Figure 3.7. Each design had its own pros and cons as described below:

- **Design 01A:** Triangular based shape allows to rotate the device around the axis of the shelf bar over the shelf area and to keep the footprint of the hydroponic installation small. The result is a space efficient unit design.
- **Design 01B:** For better interaction this shape can be also rotated towards outside of the shelf while still occupying limited space.
- **Design 02:** An elongated form factor helps to avoid occupying space outside and inside the shelf footprint. The result is least interference with the environment. The interaction with the device is slightly compromised.
- **Design 03:** Increasing the housing footprint might also reduce the vertical space needed for the battery, inner components and create a more lateral interaction direction.

Design 01A was chosen as the most user-friendly and space-efficient design.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3.6 (a) Photograph of the first GOhydro hydroponic installation at the premises of SciO (Athens, Greece) featuring broccoli (top tier) and 3 types of basil (lower tier; from left to right: *Ocimum basilicum*, *Ocimum basilicum Purpurescens* and *Ocimum basilicum “Mammoth”*), (b) schematic showing the with the red dot the optimum location for the placement of the all-in-in-one CHSK, and (c) close up photograph of the CHSK placement location showing the curved elements.

Figure 3.7. The four designs considered for the mounting of the CHSK on the hydroponic installation. Design 01A was chosen as the optimum one.

2. Interaction during operation – Status notification

For the buttons, our aim was to have one button only (instead of the initial thought of two separate buttons) that combines the button and the LED status indicator (as shown below). Different pressing patterns could enable different functionalities with one button only.

3. Charging

Based on the selection of the Xiaomi Redmi Fast Charge 20000mAh as the charging unit for both the CHSK and the CSU, four designs and concepts were scrutinized along with their advantages and challenges (Figure 3.8):

- **CHARGE ON SITE – 01.** *Advantages:* No big battery door is needed in order to take out the battery and this avoids exposure of components to the humidity. *Challenges:* The battery switch must be accessible to start with the battery operating with a USB cable limited in length; Status LEDs on the battery must be visible from outside in order to allow users to properly manage the battery charging; the sealing

must be secured when the device is operating, with e.g. a rubber cap,-during charging, the sealed volume may be compromised

- **TAKE OUT BATTERY -02.** *Advantages:* The battery can be easily detached when the top cover is removed; the battery compartment can be closed when the battery is charged; The device can work with multiple batteries. *Challenges:* The sealing between device housing and the top cover must be secured; If the battery is removed towards the top, it requires clearance in the area above the device.
- **DETACH BATTERY UNIT – 03.** *Advantages:* The battery unit can be easily removed; The battery can be store well inside the battery unit housing; the device can work with multiple batteries. *Challenges:* The sealing between device housing and the battery unit must be secured; LED and battery button must be accessible (at least when battery unit is removed); if the battery is removed towards the top, it requires clearance in the area above the device.; the rest of the unit must be re-capped or attached with another battery unit in order to stay sealed.
- **DETACH WHOLE UNIT – 04.** *Advantages:* The challenge of sealing the device will be decreased as the battery will be exposed only during charging, when it is removed from the shelf; easy attachment will allow to attach and remove the full device which can be suitable also for other purposes than charging. *Challenges:* Difficult to handle the full device with tubes and sensors that are partially submerged in the water everytime the battery needs to be charged; The unit cannot operate whilst the battery is charged; Attachment feature must be easy to attach and detach and lock the full unit securely

In terms of ergonomony scenarios 1 and 4 were discarded, while scenarios 2 and 3 were deemed by all partners of the consortium more user-friendly and closer to eh COhydro vision. Finally, scenario 2 was chosen and implemented in the final design.

Figure 3.8. Overview of the four charging unit scenarios

As a final step in the design process, 5 variations of the GOhydro CHSK unit were created taking into account all the above consideration, requirements and constraints. The five variations are shown collectively for comparison purposes in Figure 3.9, while details of each design may be found in the Annex. It should be noted that each design variation had its own sub-depending on the various aspects that were important to each design (see Annex).

Figure 3.9. Overview of the 5 design variations for the all-in-one-CHSK unit.

An ideation workshop was organized by nr21 to present all details of all the concepts. After reviewing of all details, the final design shown in Figures 3.10-3.11 contained an amalgamation of Designs 01A-01C.

Figure 3.10. Visualizations from the ideation process for the concrete design solution.

Figure 3.11. Visualizations of the matured All-in-one Sensor Kit concept ready for 3D printing.

In the meantime we have received all components in physical form and continue to work out the case datasets. This also happens with the help of 3D printing. In the further development phases of the project, we will, if necessary, slightly adapt the components again and also optimize the wiring of the printed circuit boards so that they fit even better into the desired housing shape. The communications and storage unit is also being worked out in this context and finalized by appropriate prototype iterations. The current development status can be understood using the following visualizations.

This entire exercise meticulously performed for the CHSK unit facilitated immensely the design of the CSU. Of course, the design constraints for CSU were less stringent and complicated. As a result the CSU is already being assembled. Figure 3.12a depicts the final design and Figure 12b shows the first prototyping with 3d-printed components.

The CHSK is currently being assembled and it will be shipped back to Greece for the first test runs. Replicates will be realized for the other installations in Romania and Denmark as soon as its operation is verified and validated at the Greek installation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.12. (a) Preliminary visualizations of the CSU and (b) Photograph of the first prototyping tests

4 CONCLUSIONS

D2.3 was successfully completed albeit a slight, but deliberate delay unanimously opted by the consortium. It was deemed important to exhaust all design scenarios to provide the best fitted solution that could transform the GOhydro vision of an easily-deployable DIY kit for urban farming. It is expected that the CHSK and CSU prototypes will be installed with 1 month delay (M13 instead of M12) at the first hydroponic installation at the premises of SciO (Greece).

ANNEX - DETAILS OF THE 5 CHSK DESIGNS

CONCEPT 1A

n21*

IDEATION
CONCEPT 01 A

The top of the battery can also be varied in terms of materials or surface texture:

1. Variant with matte opaque top cover matching the rest of the housing.
2. Variant with transparent top cover.
3. Variant with top cover with linear surface texture.

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CONCEPT 1B

01

No window for the status LED of the battery. This will help the sealing quality of the housing. Depending on the location of the device, this window might not be very useful for a quick check, especially as you might need to press a button to have the battery status indicated.

02

Small opening must be covered by a transparent material. The small size will limit the size of the transparent material and thus the material could be a foil.

03

A large window to check the battery status will help to identify the battery status more easily when LEDs are on. The transparent material might need to be more stiff.

CONCEPT 1C

CONCEPT 2

Quick release locking mechanism

CONCEPT 3

